

Educational Impact of MP-ASI Role on Growth on Balita Stunting in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang

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ABSTRACT

A change in the behavior of parents in giving MP-ASI can be done through a booster factor that is the health officer who provides health education. The aim of this research is to find out the influence of the educational role of MP-ASI on growth in stunting youngsters. This type of research is a quasi-experiment with the design of One Group Pre-Test - Post-test Design Without Control Groups. The population is the mothers who have stunts aged 6-59 months in Puskesmas Ujoh by 2022 as many as 12 people. Sampling techniques use total sampling, so samples are equal to populations. Analysis of data using paired sample t test. There is an influence of educational role MP-ASI on growth in stunting news.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of nutrition becomes a vital issue in the life cycle to be addressed immediately. Malnutrition can occur from the fetus in the womb to the beginning of the child's life. (1000 Hari Pertama Kehidupan). Causes of malnutrition generally include low intake of vitamins and minerals required by the body, poor access to nutritious foods, and poor food diversity and animal protein sources. One of the most frequently occurring nutritional problems is short stunts.(Kemenkes RI, 2018).

Stunting is a condition in which a child fails to grow due to malnutrition for a long time, so that a child grows shorter than a normal child of his or her age. Children are classified as stunts when height or height is generally lower than the national standards contained in the Mother and Child Health Book (KIA) and some other documents. In addition to inhibiting the child's growth and being susceptible to disease, stunting also affects brain development that makes child intelligence unoptimal, thus risking reduced child productivity as an adult.(Kemenkes RI, 2018). The impact of stunting on children will affect the human resource culture in the future. As a nation that is struggling to carry out a fair and equitable national development, it will require reliable support of the SDM. The need of such a reliable SDM will surely be difficult to meet when many of the children of the nation's successors suffer stunting. Therefore, the Government has established a National Strategy for Accelerating Stunting Prevention in 2018-2024.

The prevalence of stunting in 2017 in the world is about 150.8 million newbies or about 22% newbies. Africa accounts for more than a quarter, 39% and more than half of the world's stunting news comes from Asia (55%). There are approximately 83.6 million stopping news in Asia. Central Asia has contributed at least 0.9% and the largest proportion comes from South Asia (58.7%). Stunting news prevalence data collected by the WHO (World Health Organization) show that Indonesia is among the third country with the highest prevalence of stunting in the Southeast Asia/South East Asia Regional (SEAR) region.(Kemenkes RI, 2018).

The prevalence of stunting news in Indonesia in 2007 was 36.8%, in 2010 35.6%, in 2013 37.2%, in 2018 30.8% (Maliki, 2019), then in 2021 reached 24.4%. This figure is high when compared to the WHO standard of a maximum of 20% (Priambodo, 2022).The prevalence in Eastern Kalimantan in 2018 is high: 30% consists of overstunting of 18% and very stunting of 12%". (Priambodo, 2022).

According to Priambodo (2022) by 2021, the prevalence of Mahakam Ulu district has reached 7,03 per cent. Although prevalence has declined, stunting is still a challenge for the government, as the target for the rate of stunting prevalence in the National Medium-Range Development Plan is 14 per cent by 2024, so further stunting efforts still need to be made to ensure that children can grow and develop optimally and to the maximum, accompanied by emotional, social, and physical abilities ready to learn, as well as being able to innovate and compete at a global level. There are three things to be taken into account in stunting prevention, namely, improvements to diet, care patterns, as well as improvements in sanitation and access to clean water", non-health issues are at

the root of stunting problems, whether they are economic, political, social, cultural, poverty, lack of empowerment of women, and environmental degradation. Therefore, the role of all sectors and the order of society, especially pregnant mothers and mothers who have newborns who have entered the time given Mother's Milk Accompanying Food (MP-ASI) is needed to be able to gain an understanding of the importance of nutritional intake, mother's behavior as well as the right methods of parenting in mothers with newborns to support the growth of the child.

After the baby is 6 months old, the need for nutrients increases with the growth and development of the baby, while the production of milk begins to decrease, so the baby needs additional foods as a milk companion.(Arini, 2017).

According to a preliminary study of Puskesmas Ujoh in 2022, there were 12 stunting newspapers aged between 6-24 months, there were 2 people and between 25-59 months there were 10 people. The age was the entry age in MP-ASI. Through an initial interview with the new mother, he presented the MP-ASE given to the child in the form of slender rice with the same patch of pauk as the parents but smoothed and there was also that gave the child MP-asi in an instant form. Besides, there are parents who said that their child is difficult to eat, does not want to consume vegetables, so only a lot of formula milk was given. This may indicate a lack of mother's knowledge of the role of giving MP-ASI for good news. To improve mother's knowledge, there needs to be an education of MP-ASE role. A change in parents' behavior in giving MP-ASI can be done through the strengthening factor of the health officer who provides health education. The method of health education carried out by the health officer is basically an approach used in the educational process to deliver a message to the health education objectives, i.e. individuals, groups/families, and communities. The learning method in health education can be individual education, group education method, and mass education method. (Suliha et al, 2017).

Health education can be done with different media. The media is used to facilitate the delivery of messages to the educational target, which can be a leaflet media. The advantage of the media leaflet is that it uses a short and clear language so that its contents are easy to understand, designed systematically with illustrations so that it attracts the attention of the reader, because its shape is small, easy to carry anywhere. (Kristianto, 2018).

In a two-week study conducted in Surakarta in connection with the administration of MP-ASI to children aged 6-24 months with approval, it showed that the nutritional status of the child increased by 0.39 kg in the age of 6-11 months and an increase of 0.49 kg in a group of kids aged 12-24 months. Nutritional approval has an influence on the mental patterns and the level of care of the mother to provide adequate nutritional intake for her child.(Marfuah,2017).Fauziah (2020) suggests that there is a relationship between the history of administration and the frequency of administration of MP-ASI as well as the dietary patterns of energy, zinc, and substance adequacy with the occurrence of stunts.

Based on observations on the work area of Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang, there has been no education on the role of MP-ASI against the growth of stunting news. Through the explanation, the researchers are interested in doing research on "Education Impact of the Role of MP -ASI Against the Growth of Stunting News in Puskésmas Ujah Bilang Year 2023".

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Stunting

Stunting is a condition in which a young child has a growth impairment due to chronic malnutrition and a child is too young for his or her age. Malnutrition can occur from the time the child is in the womb and in the early stages of birth, but the stunting condition in the newborn is visible after the age of two. Stunted and severely stunted balls are those whose height (TB/U) or length (PB/U), depending on their age, is shorter than the WHO-MGRS (Multicentre Growth Reference Study) 2006 standard. The Ministry of Health (Kemenkes) defines stunting as a young child whose z-score is less than -2SD/standard deviation (short) and less than -3SD (very short) (Riskesmas, 2018).

MP ASI

Early breastfeeding (MP-ASI) is food or drink given to a baby aged 6 months. (Nurwiah, 2017). The World Health Organization (WHO) defines Mother's Milk Water (MMA) as exclusive when babies are only given breast milk without any additional food and/or beverages, except vitamins and medicines. (Nurwiah, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative research. The research method used is experimental study. The research project uses the One Group Pre-Test - Post-test Design Without Control Group. The population of this study is a mother who has a stunting baby aged 6-59 months in Puskesmas Ujoh By 2022 as many as 12 people. Sampling using total sampling. This research will be carried out in February 2023 at Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang. The instruments used were questionnaires, height and weight measurements and leaflets.

The data obtained will be processed and the results will be displayed as a percentage of the frequency distribution table using the univariate analysis formula. The data is then processed with the help of computerization using statistical tests. Where the bi-variation test in this study uses a paired sample t test with a thickness limit of $\alpha=0,05$.

RESULTS

Univariat Analysis

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents

No	Karakteristik Responden	N	%
1	Usia Balita		
	6-24 bulan	2	16,7
	25-59 bulan	10	83,3

2	Jenis Kelamin Balita		
	Laki-laki	4	33,3
	Perempuan	8	66,7
3	Usia Ibu		
	21-25 tahun	2	16,7
	26-30 tahun	7	58,3
	31-35 tahun	3	25
4	Pendidikan Ibu		
	Tamat SD	2	16,7
	Tamat SMP	4	33,3
	Tamat SMA	6	50
5	Pekerjaan Ibu		
	IRT	7	58,3
	Pedagang/Wiraswasta	2	16,7
	Petani/Nelayan	1	8,3
	Karyawan Swasta	2	16,7

Sumber : Data Primer, 2023

Based on table 1, it was obtained that of the 12 mothers who had stunting news aged 6-59 months in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang, mostly with young people aged between 25 and 59 months were 10 people (83.3%), the sex of the news are 8 women (66.7%), the mother's age between 26 and 30 years is 7 people (58.3%), maternal education of high school graduates is 6 people (50%), the job of mothers as IRT is 7 persons (58.3%).

Table 2. Growth of news before giving education role MP-ASI to mothers who have news stunting in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang

No	<i>Pre Test</i>	N	%
1	Gizi Buruk	5	41,7
2	Gizi Kurang	7	58,3
	Jumlah	12	100

Sumber : Data Primer, 2023

Based on table 2 it was obtained that the growth of young people before giving education role MP-ASI in mothers who have stunting young people in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang, mostly under-nutrition of 7 people (58.3%), while poor nutrition of 5 people (41.7%).

Table 3. Growth of news after giving education role MP-ASI to mothers who have news stunting in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang

No	<i>Post Test</i>	N	%
1	Gizi Kurang	3	25
2	Gizi Baik	9	75
	Jumlah	12	100

Sumber : Data Primer, 2023

Based on table 3, it was obtained that the growth of young people after giving education role MP-ASI in mothers who have stunting young people in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang, mostly good nutrition was 9 people (75%), while nutrition less was 3 people (25%).

Table 4. The educational influence of the role of MP-ASI on growth in stunting news in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang

Variabel	Pengukuran	Mean ±SD	Beda Mean	t	p
Pertumbuhan Balita Stunting	<i>Pre test</i>	10,1833±1,86442	1,1167	6,466	0,000
	<i>Post test</i>	11,3000±1,78987			

Sumber : Data Primer, 2023

Based on table 4 obtained mean difference between news growth before giving education role MP-ASI in mothers who have stunting news in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang with after giving education roles MP-ASE in moths who have news stunting in Puskesmas U joh Bilang of 1,1167 kg and p value $0,000 < 0,05$, which means H_a received that there is an influence of education of role MP -ASI on growth on news stopping in Pushesmas ujoh Biling.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the research it is known that the difference between the growth of the news before giving education role MP-ASI in mothers who have stunting news in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang with after giving education of the role MP -ASI in the mother who has news stunting in Puskesmas U joh Bilang of 1,1167 kg and p value $0,000 < 0,05$, which means H_a received that there is an influence of education role of MP-asi on the growth on the news stopping in Pushesmas ujoh bilang.

The results of this study are in line with previous studies conducted by Masri (2020) showing that the intervention of the combination of PMT and Nutrition Counseling has an impact on the nutritional status of children under the age of 6 - 24 months. Irwan Research (2020) shows that the administration of the modification of the PMT intervention is effective on the improvement of the nutrition status of young people under the work area of Puskesmas Paguyaman district of Boalemo. Marfuah Research (2017) showed that intervention for 2 weeks associated with the provision of MP-ASI in children aged 6-24 months with the given approval, showed an improvement in nutritional state which is a significant increase in weight of 0.39 kg in children ages 6-11 months and an increase of 0.49 kg in the group of children aging 12-24 months. Nutrition determination has an influence on the mother's mindset and level of care to provide the right dietary intake for her child.

Stunting is caused by poor recovery and unstable growth thus inhibiting optimal growth. This situation suggests that a group of babies born with a normal weight can suffer from stunting if the nutritional requirements required to grow a baby are not met. (Kemenkes RI, 2018).

One of the most serious and common factors affecting stunting is malnutrition, especially in young children, which is caused by nutrient deficiencies due to food deficiencies and barriers to the absorption of nutrients. Nutrients are used by the body as a source of energy available in foods that contain carbohydrates and proteins that the body uses as building materials that serve to repair the body's cells. Unhealthy food intake, lack of energy and

protein intake are the direct causes of growth impairment in children. (Irianto, 2018).

Important nutritional intake is obtained by the newborn to meet nutritional needs other than milk, baby needs mother's milk food or commonly called MP-ASI which is given to the baby at the age of 6-24 months and contains nutrients to grow the baby flower. MP-ASI is a baby's transition food to recognize household food. During the first six months, breastfeeding can still provide the baby's nutritional needs, but after that milk production will decrease so that the nutritional requirements of the baby are no longer covered by milk alone. MP-ASI hygiene and poor sanitation can lead to microbial contamination that can increase the risk of other infection in the baby. Milk MP can be prepared specifically for babies or can use food like family food, but consistency is appropriate to the age and ability of babies to receive food (Mufida dkk, 2018).

The poor nutritional intake of the young, due to the poor level of mother's knowledge. The level of nutritional knowledge greatly influences changes in one's attitudes and behavior in choosing food ingredients, and also affects the nutritional status of the individual involved. Poor nutrition in a region determines the high prevalence of malnutrition in that country. (Irianto, 2018).

Improving mother's knowledge can be achieved through the education of the role of MP. Health education can be done with different media. The media is used to facilitate the delivery of messages to educational targets, which may include leaflet media. The advantage of the media leaflet is that it uses a short and clear language so that its contents are easy to understand, designed systematically with illustrations so that it attracts the attention of the reader, because its shape is small, easy to carry anywhere. (Kristianto, 2018).

The researchers assume that there is an educational influence of the role of MP-ASI on growth in stunting news in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang. This is due to health education activities, conducted by counseling using leaflets to mothers who have news aged 6-59 months such as knowledge about MP-ASE good for news as well as giving Additional Food such as biscuits and vegetable menu to eat at home, making nutritional intake of news better that has an impact on weight gain.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion and description then conclusion Results of statistical tests There is an influence of educational role MP-ASI on growth in stunting news in Puskesmas Ujoh Bilang (p value $0,001 < \alpha : 0,05$).

The results of this research are expected to further enhance the efforts of dissemination to both individuals and families, especially mothers who have stunting news to give a good MP-ASI to their children to grow optimally as well as improve cross-sector and cross-program cooperation in reducing stunting incidents.

FURTHER STUDY

As for the advice that can be given to further researchers, to investigate other factors that influence the occurrence of stunting news.

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REFERENCES

- Almatsier, Sunita. 2018. *Prinsip Dasar Ilmu Gizi*. Jakarta : PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Achadi. 2018. *Global Nutrition Report (Action and Accountability to Accelerate the World's Progress on Nutrition), Masalah Gizi di Indonesia dan posisinya secara Global*. Diseminasi Global Nutrition Report dalam Rangka Peringatan Hari Gizi Nasional 2015.
- Arikunto. 2018. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Arini, Firlia Ayu. 2017. *Pengaruh Pelatihan Pemberian MP ASI Kepada Ibu dengan Anak Baduta Di Kecamatan Sukmajaya Kota Depok Terhadap Pengetahuan dan Perilaku Pemberian MP ASI*. *Jurnal Kedokteran dan Kesehatan*, Vol.13, No. 1,
- Dinas Kesehatan Provinsi Kaltim. 2020. *Profil Kesehatan Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*. Samarinda : Pusdatin.
- Ilmanisak, Ragita. 2017. *Pengaruh edukasi MPASI terhadap tingkat pengetahuan dan sikap ibu serta tingkat konsumsi energi dan protein baduta stunting usia 7-24 bulan*. *Jurnal Pendidikan Kesehatan* Vol 6 No. 1.
- Irianto. 2018. *Gizi Seimbang dalam Kesehatan Reproduksi (Balanced. Nutrition in Reproductive Health)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Kemendes RI. 2018. *Buletin Stunting Di Indonesia*. Jakarta. Indonesia. <http://www.depkes.go.id/>.
- Khomsan Ali. 2016. *Pangan Dan Gizi Untuk Kesehatan*. Jakarta : PT.Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Kristianto. 2018. *Studi Komparasi Media Komik dan Media Papan Lembar Balik (Flipchart) Terhadap Hasil Belajar IPA Siswa Kelas III SDN01*

WinongKecamatan Winong Kabupaten Pati Tahun 2014/2015. Naskah Publikasi Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.

Maliki. 2019. *Stunting*. maliki@bappenas.go.id.

Marfuah D, Kurniawati I. 2017. *Upaya Peningkatan Pengetahuan Ibu tentang MP Asi dengan Edukasi Gizi Melalui Booklet*. URECOL (University Res Colloquium).

McLEOD. 2018. *Sistem Informasi Edisi 7 Jilid 2*. Prenhallindo. Jakarta.

Moehji, S. 2019. *Ilmu Gizi 2*. Jakarta : Penerbit Papas Sinar Sinarti.

Mufida, dkk. 2018. *Prinsip dasar makanan pendamping air susu ibu (MP-ASI) untuk bayi usia 6-24 Bulan*. Jurnal Pangan dan Agroindustri Vol.3 No 4 p.1646-1651.

Nindrea, Ricvan Dana. 2017. *Pengaruh penyuluhan Gizi Dengan Perubahan Perilaku Sarapan Pagi Siswa Sekolah Dasar*. Jurnal Endurance 2(3).

Notoatmodjo, S. 2017. *Promosi Kesehatan dan Ilmu Perilaku*. PT Rineka Cipta. Jakarta. 2017. *Metodologi Penelitian Kesehatan*. Rineka Cipta. Jakarta.

Nursalam. 2018. *Konsep dan penerapan metodologi penelitian ilmu keperawatan : pedoman skripsi, tesis, dan instrument penelitian keperawatan*. Jakarta : Salemba Medika.

Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan Nomor 23/2014 tentang Upaya Perbaikan Gizi.

Perpres Nomor 42 Tahun 2013 tentang Gerakan Nasional Percepatan Perbaikan Gizi

Pramuditya. 2017. *Kaitan Antara Tingkat Pendidikan dan Pengetahuan Gizi Ibu, Serta Pola Asuh dengan Perilaku Keluarga Sadar Gizi dan Status Gizi*. Bogor : Departemen Gizi Masyarakat Dan Sumberdaya Keluarga, Fakultas Pertanian, Institut Pertanian Bogor.

Priambodo. 2022. *Prevalensinya Rendah, Bupati Tetap Komitmen Hapuskan Stunting di Mahulu*. <https://kaltimkece.id/pariwara/pariwaramahakam-ulu/prevalensinya-rendah-bupati-tetap-komitmen-hapuskan-stunting-di-mahulu>.

RANPG atau Rencana Aksi Nasional Pangan dan Gizi Tahun 2016-2019

Renstra Badan Kependudukan dan Keluarga Berencana Nasional (BKKBN) 2015-2019

Riset Kesehatan Dasar Provinsi Kalimantan Timur. 2018. Laporan *Riskesdas Provinsi Kalimantan Timur*. Depkes RI. Kaltim.

RPJM atau Rencana Pembangunan Jangka Menengah 2015–2019.

RPJMN atau Rencana Pembangunan Jangka Panjang Nasional 2005–2025.

Sugiyono. 2020. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung. Alfabeta.

Suliha *et al*, 2017. *Pendidikan Kesehatan dalam Keperawatan Cetakan I*. Jakarta : EGC.

Supariasa. 2018. *Penilaian Status Gizi*. Jakarta ; Buku Kedokteran EGC. UU Nomor 36/2009 tentang Kesehatan

Widyavihusna, Elsa. 2021. *Pengaruh edukasi gizi dengan aplikasi whatsapp melalui media video dan ceramah terhadap pengetahuan ibu tentang pola pemberian MP-ASI pada balita usia 6-12 bulan di Puskesmas Gunung Alam Bengkulu Utara*. Skripsi Poltekkes Kemenkes Bengkulu)